

Mobile Technologies applied to protect victims of a crime within the EU Area of Justice: RightsApp for e-Justice

D5.6 Report on the dissemination activities and their impact into the targeted groups

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ACRONYMS LIST:

- EFUS: European Forum for Urban Security
- EU: European Union
- FEPSU: Spanish Forum for the Prevention and Urban Security
- ISS: International Support Service

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document reports the impact of the dissemination activities with a quantifiable number of reads, downloads, views, among others. The dissemination activities were listed in RightsApp Deliverable D5.8 – “Dissemination in social media and in the project’s home page”, this document completes D5.8 with the evaluation of these dissemination activities.

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1 INTRODUCTION

This document reports the impact of the dissemination activities into the targeted groups. The impact is measured in the total number of views and/or downloads of the shared materials through different channels and it is aimed at tuning up the dissemination strategy by raising strong and weak points of this strategy, allowing the RightsApp research team to implement the required modifications in order to optimize dissemination in the period that goes beyond the funding span. This deliverable is complemented with the RightsApp Deliverable D5.8 – “Dissemination in social media and in the project’s home page”. Deliverable D5.8 shows how the RightsApp project achievements and main outcomes were disseminated (News text, tweet, public report, mobile app code, among others) and which channel was used for each particular dissemination activity (RightsApp home page, news section of a collaborating entity, Twitter account, Zenodo Community, among others).

This document is structured as follows: Section 2 lists and reports the number of visits and/or downloads of the dissemination materials that the RightsApp research team made publicly available in the RightsApp home page; Section 3 lists the number of views and downloads of each document uploaded to the RightsApp Zenodo Community; the International Support Service has adopted the RightsApp mobile applications as part of its Emergency Protocol, Section 4 reports the number of citizens reached through the ISS’s Emergency Protocol; Section 5 shows statistics of the RightsApp Twitter profile; Section 6 addresses statistics of installation and active users regarding RightsApp mobile applications; and finally Section 7 shows statistics about how the project’s collaborators have disseminated the RightsApp project.

2 RIGHTSAPP HOME PAGE

The RightsApp Home Page has become the main source for the dissemination of the project’s achievements and the sharing of public documents. In this section we report usage statistics of the home page since these statistics shows how the project has reached the targeted groups.

Figure 1 depicts different kind of statistics gathered through Google Analytics for the period from July 1st, 2020 to September 7th, 2020. The top graphic outlines the number of page views within the reporting period which has upward and downward movements. In this period, a total number of 127 users (122 were new users, 87.8%) connected to the RightsApp home page and viewed a total number of 278 pages. On average, each session¹ opened 1.84 pages, the session duration was 1 minute, and 39 seconds and each user opened 1.19 sessions per user. The bounce rate is defined by single-page sessions in which there was no interaction with the page, within the considered period of time the bounce rate reported is 66.23%.

Figure 1: RightsApp home page statistics from 1st July 2020 to 7th September 2020

Figure 2 lists the top countries where connections to the RightsApp home page comes from. Taking into account the 127 users reported within the period from July 1st, 2020 to September 7th, 2020, Spain was the origin of the 78.74% of the connections, followed by United States and China.

Country	Users	% Users
1. Spain	100	78.74%
2. United States	16	12.60%
3. China	3	2.36%
4. Germany	2	1.57%
5. France	2	1.57%
6. Australia	1	0.79%
7. Switzerland	1	0.79%
8. United Kingdom	1	0.79%
9. Poland	1	0.79%

Figure 2: List of countries where connections to the RightsApp home page comes from

¹ Session: A session is the period time a user is actively engaged with the website.

Figure 3 outlines statistics for the 278 page views reported in this time frame. The main page was the most viewed (“/”²) and the landing page of the most part of the connections to the RightsApp home page (“Entrances”). Then, the following pages in the ranking considering the total number of page views are the “Online infoday presentations”³ and the page for the download of the mobile applications (“RightsApp applications”⁴). They share a 15% of the total number of page views. Tutorial videos (“RightsApp training videos”⁵) reached 13.67% of the page views. The news section (“News”⁶) represents the 7.55% of the total number of page views. On average, the time spent on each page is 1 min and 57 seconds. However, the time on online infoday reached 4 min connection.

Page	Page Views	Unique Page Views	Avg. Time on Page	Entrances	Bounce Rate	% Exit
	278 % of Total: 100.00% (278)	219 % of Total: 100.00% (219)	00:01:57 Avg for View: 00:01:57 (0.00%)	151 % of Total: 100.00% (151)	66.23% Avg for View: 66.23% (0.00%)	54.32% Avg for View: 54.32% (0.00%)
1. /	104 (37.41%)	74 (33.79%)	00:01:30	67 (44.37%)	50.75%	45.19%
2. /index.php/rightsapp-infoday-presentation/	43 (15.47%)	35 (15.98%)	00:04:00	29 (19.21%)	79.31%	72.09%
3. /index.php/rightsapp-applications/	41 (14.75%)	32 (14.61%)	00:00:59	12 (7.95%)	41.67%	53.66%
4. /index.php/rightsapp-training-videos/	38 (13.67%)	35 (15.98%)	00:02:12	33 (21.85%)	87.88%	81.58%
5. /index.php/news/	21 (7.55%)	12 (5.48%)	00:02:11	0 (0.00%)	0.00%	14.29%
6. /index.php/articles/	6 (2.16%)	6 (2.74%)	00:00:31	1 (0.66%)	100.00%	50.00%
7. /index.php/project-structure/	6 (2.16%)	6 (2.74%)	00:04:16	1 (0.66%)	0.00%	33.33%
8. /index.php/project-identity-set/	4 (1.44%)	4 (1.83%)	00:00:00	0 (0.00%)	0.00%	100.00%
9. /index.php/consortium/	2 (0.72%)	2 (0.91%)	00:00:14	0 (0.00%)	0.00%	0.00%

Figure 3: Ranking of the pages visited in the RightsApp home page from 1st July 2020 to 7th September 2020

In the last 28-day period, a total number of 45 unique users had at least one session on the RightsApp home page. In addition, within the 14-day period 11 unique users had at least one session on the RightsApp home page. That means that 45 unique users returned to the website in a 28-days and 11 unique users came back to the website in a 14-days period.

Figure 4: Number of active users in the last 14 and 45 days from the July 1st, 2020 to September 7th, 2020

² Main page of the RightsApp home page available at: <http://rightsapp-project.uab.cat/>
³ Online infoday presentations page is available at: <http://rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/rightsapp-infoday-presentation/>
⁴ RightsApp mobile applications download page is available at: <http://rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/rightsapp-applications/>
⁵ RightsApp training videos page is available at: <http://rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/rightsapp-training-videos/>
⁶ News section of the RightsApp home page is available at: <http://rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/news/>

3 ZENODO COMMUNITY

Zenodo is a general-purpose open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program⁷ and operated by CERN⁸. It allows researchers to upload and make data sets, software, reports, and any other research related digital artifacts available. For each uploaded item, a persistent digital object identifier is assigned, which makes the stored items easily citable. The RightsApp project Zenodo community is currently composed by 12 documents. More documents will be added as they become available.

Table 1 lists the documents uploaded to the RightsApp Zenodo community that reports the name of the document, the upload date, and the number of downloads and views for each document. As a result, at the time of writing this document, the total number of downloads for the documents in the Zenodo community is 325, and the total number of views is 608.

Deliverable title	Upload date	Downloads	Views
D2.1 – Report on key sources for the project	05/06/2018	48	54
D1.3 – Project Website	03/08/2018	36	57
D1.1 – Data Management Plan	31/08/2018	38	69
D2.3 – Questionnaire and parameters	30/11/2018	26	65
D2.4 – Translation of the particle into different languages	31/12/2018	30	44
D5.1 – Dissemination package	05/01/2019	35	71
D3.2 – RightsApp Android application	30/05/2019	19	13
D3.3 – RightsApp iOS application	30/05/2019	19	24
D4.1 – Dissemination package to targeted groups	28/08/2019	9	26
D5.4 – Mid-project International Workshop	18/11/2019	34	62
D5.9 – Final project International Workshop	06/08/2020	16	88
D5.5 – Four or more training sessions	03/09/2020	6	10
D5.8 – Dissemination in social media and in the project’s home page	08/09/2020	7	22
D5.7 – Public events	08/09/2020	2	3
Total:		325	608

Table 1: Downloads and views of the documents uploaded to the RightsApp Zenodo Community

⁷ OpenAIRE mission is to provide unlimited, barrier free, open access to research outputs financed by public funding in Europe. OpenAIRE Home Page is available at: <https://www.openaire.eu/>

⁸ CERN Home Page is available at: <https://home.cern/>

4 INTERNATIONAL SUPPORT SERVICE

The International Support Service's (ISS, formerly International Welcome Point) main target is to provide information for students, teachers, and administrative and service staff from other countries. At the ISS, newcomers: (i) will find all the information they need upon arrival; (ii) will be able to find answers to any questions about academic life; (iii) get the UAB student card; (iv) learn about the activities that take place on campus; (v) find out about available scholarships; (vi) receive personalized attention to find accommodation (vii) inquire about the university's services and, (viii) see which language courses they can enrol in. At the ISS, people from abroad will also find information on how to get to the UAB, information about accommodation, the cost of living, services on campus, as well as important phone numbers. It has been very active until March 2019, before the university facilities had to close because of Covid-19.

The ISS offers in its home page an Emergency protocol to support people from abroad that face a problem once they are living in Barcelona. Figure 5 is a screenshot that shows this protocol and the available institutions that could provide support if needed. After the publication of the RightsApp mobile application, RightsApp became part of it. The Emergency protocol is publicly available at: <https://www.uab.cat/web/mobility-international-exchange/international-support-service/travelabroad-1345819434765.html>

The most relevant fact here is that the ISS has adopted the RightsApp mobile applications as part of its Emergency Protocol.

Figure 5: International Support Service Emergency Protocol web page

5 TWITTER

The dissemination strategy implemented from the beginning of the project entailed the creation and update of a twitter account for the project (@p_rightsapp). The main objective of this account is to share the achievements and project outcomes with the general public, scholars and stakeholders. Every day the twitter account is becoming more and more active since dissemination materials, achievements and project outcomes are now available. Although in the last 28-days period the number of followers has increased significantly, the total number is still too low (12 followers). Clearly the dissemination strategy could be improved. Currently, to minimize its impact, the strategy is to use the twitter accounts of the Institute of Law and Technology, UAB Faculty of Law and UAB as multipliers. With this strategy, the RightsApp Twitter profile earned in the last 28-days period a total of 1.2K impressions⁹ (42 impressions per day). Figure 6 depicts the distribution of impressions within the reported period.

Figure 6: Number of impressions earned by the RightsApp Twitter account in the last 28-days period

Figure 7 sums up the activity of the RightsApp Twitter account during the month of August 2020. In this period the top tweet was the 2nd RightsApp Workshop report that earned 490 impressions with 5 retweets and 4 likes. In the reported month, the project twitter account gathered a total of 1370 impressions and gained 2 new followers.

Figure 7: Summary of the activity from the RightsApp Twitter account during August 2020

⁹ Impression: Number of times user saw the Tweet on Twitter

In general terms, the ranking of the top tweets sorted by the total number of impressions is listed in Figure 8. The 2nd RightsApp Workshop has reached the 644 impressions and 13 engagements¹⁰. Then, the online infoday announcement and the publication of the RightsApp mobile applications compose the top 3 ranking of tweets.

The RightsApp research team is committed to continue developing the project beyond the funding period jointly with the institution that have been collaborating with the project until now. Therefore, we expect that the twitter account will be more and more active every day as we disseminate the project results and future objectives.

¹⁰ Engagements: Total number of times a user has interacted with a Tweet. This includes all clicks anywhere on the Tweet (including hashtags, links, avatar, username and Tweet expansion), retweets, replies, follows, and likes.

Tweets	Top Tweets	Tweets and replies	Promoted	Impressions	Engagements	Engagement rate
	RightsApp project @p_rightsapp · Aug 6 2nd and final RightsApp Workshop was held on July 23rd, 2020 via Zoom. Take a look to the report: zenodo.org/record/3974190 @franguila @FEPSU @DeLaTorreCPilar @Efusnews @bcn_ajuntament @Justiciacat @Dret_UAB @TamaritJosep @UABBarcelona			644	13	2.0%
	View Tweet activity					Promote
	RightsApp project @p_rightsapp · Jul 30 Infoday slides are now available in Spanish with and without audio explanation, and in English without audio explanation at: rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/right...			444	9	2.0%
	View Tweet activity					Promote
	RightsApp project @p_rightsapp · Jul 30 RightsApp mobile applications are published at Google Play Market and Apple Store for Android and iOS versions, respectively. play.google.com/store/apps/det... apps.apple.com/app/id15119022... Take a look to the apps and give us your feedback!			411	10	2.4%
	View Tweet activity					Promote
	RightsApp project @p_rightsapp · Aug 17 The mobile apps training videos are now available for everybody. Take a look to this tour through the RightsApp mobile apps and be aware of all its features and capabilities. rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/right... @Dret_UAB @IDT_UAB @UABBarcelona			220	10	4.5%
	View Tweet activity					Promote
	RightsApp project @p_rightsapp · Aug 10 Download the latest versions of the RightsApp mobile application, including 55 Consulates located in Barcelona (Spain). Moreover, the app also includes SIOVD's contact details (Servei de Informació i Orientació Telemàtica a la Victima de Delictes) rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/right... pic.twitter.com/9Le9SKnCDR			84	6	7.1%
	View Tweet activity					Promote
	RightsApp project @p_rightsapp · Sep 5 The International Support Service has adopted the RightsApp mobile application as one step of its Emergency Protocol for students, teachers, researchers and newcomers to the UAB. Take a look to its protocol at: uab.cat/web/movilidad-... @Dret_UAB @UABBarcelona			77	5	6.5%
	View Tweet activity					Promote
	RightsApp project @p_rightsapp · Aug 12 Check out our dissemination materials containing all the information about the project and download links of the mobile apps. Report: zenodo.org/record/3380579 Materials: rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/proj...			57	5	8.8%
	View Tweet activity					Promote
	RightsApp project @p_rightsapp · Sep 5 The RightsApp project appeared in the News section of @mossos web page. Take a look to this new and follow the QR codes to download and install the app: mossos.gencat.cat/ca/details/Not...			54	9	16.7%
	View Tweet activity					Promote
	RightsApp project @p_rightsapp · Sep 5 The RightsApp project appeared in the News section of @bcn_ajuntament Take a look to this new and follow the links to download and install the app: ajuntament.barcelona.cat/seguretativprev...			54	5	9.3%
	View Tweet activity					Promote

Figure 8: Top tweets sorted by the number of impressions

6 RIGHTSAPP MOBILE APPLICATIONS

This section reports the impact of the RightsApp mobile application in terms of installation rates in both available versions: Android and iOS. In addition, the Apple Store also offers statistics about the number of times that the app showed up in the store, the number of times used, among others.

Figure 9 outlines the total number of installations of the RightsApp mobile application for the Android version within the period from 1st of June 2020 to 31st June 2020. At the beginning of the period there was about 15 installations in Android devices and at the end of the period the RightsApp mobile application has been download and installed approximately 45 times. The increase is significant but the dissemination strategy for the project must improve in this topic to reach higher number of installations.

Figure 9: Installation rate of the RightsApp mobile application for Android version within the period from 1st of June 2020 to 31st August 2020

Figure 10 depicts the number of times that the RightsApp mobile application was used at least two seconds within the period from 1st June 2020 to 31st August 2020 for the iOS version of the mobile application. The data reports that at the end of June the mobile application was used 10 times and at the end of August it was used 29 times. Therefore, the iOS version of the mobile application was used 39 times within the reporting period.

Figure 10: Number of the times the RightsApp mobile application has been used for at least two seconds for iOS version within the period from 1st June 2020 to 31st August 2020

Figure 11 depicts the number of times that the RightsApp mobile application showed up in the App Store (impressions) within the period from 1st June 2020 to 31st August 2020. The graphic shows peaks of nearly 30 impressions but on average in the reporting period the RightsApp mobile application earned 6 impression per day on unique devices.

Figure 11: The number of times that the RightsApp mobile application showed up in the App Store (impressions) within the period from 1st of June 2020 to 31st August 2020

Finally, Figure 12 reports the total number of installations per day within the period of 1st June 2020 to 31st August 2020. At the end of the period, the RightsApp mobile application counted with 45 active installations.

Figure 12: The number of installations of the RightsApp mobile application for iOS version within the period from 1st June 2020 to 31st August 2020

7 COLLABORATORS

At the moment of writing this document, three collaborating institutions have disseminated the RightsApp project through the common dissemination channels in their web pages. The Barcelona City Council and Mossos d'Esquadra (Catalan Police, LEA, as part of the Catalan Home Affairs Department) published an announcement in their News section. Both texts contain a brief description of the project and QR codes and links to download and install the mobile app. In addition, the Department of Justice of the Public Administration of Catalonia has included the RightsApp mobile application as a resource available to citizens in the section "If you have been a victim of a crime" in its web page. The following paragraph reports the impact for the two publications for which we are able to provide statistics:

- Barcelona City Council. The Barcelona City Council reported that the News section for "Security and Prevention" topics where the RightsApp news was published is visited on average 3450 times every month. Unfortunately, they are not able to provide more accurate statistics.
- Mossos d'Esquadra (Catalan Home Affairs Department). Mossos d'Esquadra reported that news published in its intranet and in the News section devoted to the general public was viewed 380 times within the period from 7th August 2020 to 31st August 2020. At the time of writing this document, we are expecting updated information about the impact of this news.

8 CONCLUSIONS

In this section, the RightsApp research team sums up the dissemination activities reports and analyses the effectiveness of the current strategy in order to reinforce strengths and to correct weaknesses.

Strengths

- RightsApp Home Page. The 87.7% of the visitors to the RightsApp Home Page within the period from 1st June 2020 to 7th September 2020 were new users. It was during the reporting period that dissemination activities intensified (Pilot, deployment of the RightsApp mobile applications, among others, the 2nd International Workshop, among others). It means that the dissemination activities attracted new users to the main source for dissemination of project's achievements and sharing of public documents.
- RightsApp Zenodo Community. The Zenodo Community is working as the reference open and traceable site for public documents coming from the results and outcomes from the project. The RightsApp research team considers that, at the time of writing this document, the number of downloads and views are acceptable. However, in the next months the dissemination of this Community should be reinforced through the social media channels from collaborating entities.
- RightsApp included in the Emergency Protocol of the ISS. One of the most relevant strength of the dissemination strategy is the adoption of RightsApp mobile application by the ISS in its Emergency Protocol.
- Collaborators dissemination. Three collaborating entities have been multipliers of the project dissemination. The Barcelona City Council, Mossos d'Esquadra (Home Affairs Department of the Catalan Government) and the Department of Justice of the Catalan Government have published texts aimed at disseminating the RightsApp project and its main outcomes.

Weaknesses

- RightsApp Twitter account. The Twitter account reports only 12 followers. It is the weakest point in the dissemination strategy, and it should be corrected in the following months. However, the action of different institutions as multipliers such as the UAB Faculty of Law and the UAB Institute of Law and Technology (coordinating institution) has allowed that Tweets published in this social network have reached an acceptable number of people (see impression rates in Section 5). Against this background, the RightsApp research team is working on a dissemination strategy that will impact directly in the dissemination rate through the project's Twitter account, jointly with the UAB Faculty of Law, the UAB Institute of Law and Technology and the UAB. This strategy consists of: i) retaking face-to-face meetings (see RightsApp Deliverable D5.7 – "Public events"¹¹); ii) intensifying the dissemination of the project's outcomes in consulates and embassies (through Mossos d'Esquadra); and iii) undertaking intensive dissemination efforts in the tourism sector (through the Home Affairs Department of the Catalan Government). However, this sector is currently in standby in Spain due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The RightsApp research team expects that these activities bring about increasing dissemination rates of the project, especially in the project's Twitter account.

¹¹ RightsApp Deliverable D5.7 – "Public events" available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/4019187#.X1-BfJMzYXo>

- RightsApp mobile application downloads. At the time of writing this document, the RightsApp research team expected better statistics regarding the download and installation figures for both versions of the mobile application. However, the research team expects a strong increase of this figures after the dissemination strategy mentioned in the previous paragraph. It encompasses the collaboration of Justice and Home Affairs Departments of the Catalan Government, and the role of the UAB Faculty of Law and the UAB as acting multipliers within their current dissemination channels.